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CHALLENGES FOR HIGHER EDUCATION IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALISATION

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the problems of education as a factor for improving the competitive environment in the processes of global development. It focuses on the problems of higher education and technology development. The paper argues for the need for basic guidelines for understanding and practicing global education, and also as a pedagogical tool to help establish approaches to global education where they do not exist and to enrich existing ones. The content of these basic guidelines has been constructed taking into account existing practices and relationships in educational service development. There is an opportunity to discuss particular aspects of global education as the Global Education Guidelines reflect the perspectives of many stakeholders. It has also been a challenge and at the same time an enriching process to incorporate different and often opposing views into the proposed guidelines.

KEY WORDS

GLOBALIZATION, DEVELOPMENT , EDUCATION, CULTURE, MODEL AND GOVERNANCE

JEL

I20, I23, M16, O33

INTRODUCTION

One of the characteristic features of modern society is the increasing influence of globalisation processes. They are making their mark on economic, political and cultural life and contributing to the formation of new globalisation values. This is being done with the crucial role of education, which is shaping the moral and cognitive potential of future generations.

The ever-narrowing boundaries between the economic, cultural and political differences of individual countries are helping to shape common ideas about educational goals and the pathways to achieving them. The main priority is to place education in the context of the global society and to relate it to qualifying people for successful and responsible lives in the global age.¹ . **Global education is an**

¹ Scheunpflug, A. Die Konzeptionelle Weiterentwicklung des Globalen Lernens. (2007) *Jahrbuch Globales Lernen 2007/2008*. Hrsg. von VENRO, Bielefeld, p. 16.

educational perspective based on the fact that modern people live and interact in an increasingly global world. It is therefore important that education provides learners with opportunities and competencies to reflect and share their perspective and role in a globally interconnected society. One of the main researchers of globalization, T. Friedman identifies several phases of globalization, which he examines historically - Globalization 1.0, Globalization 2.0 and Globalization 3.0. The period of the last phase is associated with the predominance of technology, where the world becomes miniaturized and individuals are the driving force². Outside the phases listed is the now emerging Globalization 4.0, in which Education 4.0 is developing. It is about development in the age of innovation and should shape skills related to leadership, collaboration, digital literacy, effective communication, emotional intelligence, entrepreneurship, global citizenship, problem solving and teamwork, critical thinking, creativity and innovation, intercultural understanding, lifelong learning skills³. Globalization leads to a certain internationalization and unification of undergraduate, graduate and doctoral curricula and a convergence of formulated educational goals. Requirements can be stated that academia should recognise alternative cultural perspectives as equally valid for all regions.

The above is linked to the European Higher Education Area, created as a result of the Bologna Process to replace the subject-specific priorities of individual academia with a set of social, economic and in some cases political objectives. The situation created makes it difficult for trainees in their efforts to differentiate and defend the educational potential that is worth passing on to future generations⁴. Global education is an educational perspective that is based on the fact that modern people live and interact in an increasingly global world. This brings us to one of the challenges of contemporary higher education in the context of globalisation - the reluctance to preserve and transmit universal knowledge, intellectual heritage and historically formed values to future generations⁵.

At the same time, in each country there are educational traditions and national educational priorities that are built on specific national psychological traits. Related to this are the emphases of individual countries' education policies, which implicitly or explicitly feature particular ideas for implementing global education for building a sustainable future. Among the reasons for the process of economic globalization stands out, which necessitates the need for modern education. Thus, most countries have established a market economy that allows free enterprise as an economic model, but they also need a new type of education to meet the new needs. Global education is understood as encompassing education for development, education for human rights, education for sustainability, education for peace and the dimension of education for citizenship.

EXHIBITION

Global education is an education that opens people's eyes and minds to the realities of a globalised world and spurs them on to achieve a world with greater justice and human rights for all. Our focus, will be on higher education, but it will also be complementary to other levels of educational provision in a global society. Globalisation has implications for the levels and conditions for the development of modern education and technological developments. Closely related to the conceptual features are the particularities of higher education in each country are the guidelines for the development of school education. An example is the dual system of vocational training in Germany, which consolidates the tradition of the German education system of early specialisation and profiling of students on the basis of their achievements. The dual system focuses on the formation of practical skills needed by

² Freedman, T. (2006) *The world is flat. A Brief History of the 21st Century*, Sofia.

³ Vitanova, N. (2020) *Education of the Future*, Shumen: University Press "Bishop Konstantin Preslavski", p. 22

⁴ Young, M., Muller, J. (2016) *Curriculum and the Specialization of Knowledge: Studies in the Sociology of Education*, Abingdon: Routledge.

⁵ Williams, J. (2016) Knowledge Matters. *Review Article in Spiked Review*, March <http://www.spiked-online.com/spiked-review/article/knowledge-matters#.VwUgDBMrJT5> (07.08.2022)

enterprises and encourages cooperation between schools, enterprises and students. It focuses on vocational dual training in the recognised 350 or so professions, mainly in craft, trade, industry, services and agriculture.

The Scandinavian social model, which combines flexibility and security and seeks to achieve a balance between labour markets, goes in another direction. The achievements of the Finnish education system in the last 20 years are well known, with its practical orientation, individualisation of education according to cognitive ability and the increased prestige of the teaching profession in society. Education in Baltic Estonia is developing in a different direction, reflecting the national priority to boost the development of digital skills, high-speed internet and sophisticated IT infrastructure. The use of digital technologies has allowed the country to rank at the top of the EU Member States, in the OECD Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA)⁶. Preparations for the digitalisation of Estonian education have been ongoing for more than 25 years, starting in 1997 with the Tiigrihüpe project to provide computers and internet access for schools and digital training for teachers. In addition to digitalisation, another priority area of education in Estonia is entrepreneurship.

In the field of education, the process of globalisation has had a wide range of impacts on national education policies and is defined as the *globalisation of education*. It can also be defined as the commercialisation, privatisation and capitalisation of education at the international level⁷. This process is manifested in the following areas:

- focus on education as a mechanism for economic growth;
- Collaborative activities of intergovernmental, governmental and international non-governmental organisations in the field of education;
- the impact of information technology and the global information network;
- international evaluation in education;
- The influence of multinational corporations on global and regional education policies⁸

Thus, the globalization of the world economy poses to young people the need for their active participation in the increasing globalization of education⁹. It shifts the emphasis from local and regional educational research to macro or meso level research. In examining the impact of globalization on education at the local level, Spring reveals the systemic nature of its manifestation. He argues that global macro decisions made at the superstructure level trickle down to micro decisions made at the local level¹⁰.

Globalization brings to the fore knowledge and the possibilities to produce, transfer and apply it through information and communication technologies as the main driving force of economic and social development in the new information age. The very knowledge needed by every individual is increasing manifold, making education and the opportunities for acquiring and updating it throughout life of paramount importance. Globalisation thus has an immediate impact on the higher education system - elevating its role, but also presenting it with a number of challenges¹¹.

Today, countries around the world are striving to develop a knowledge-based economy and this has a direct effect on education policies and university and school curricula. Thus, the role of education in promoting economic growth is being appreciated, with increasing attention being paid to learning

⁶ Reflection paper on reaping the benefits of globalisation, European Commission (2017), http://devedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/reflection-paper-globalisation_bg.pdf (07.09.2022), pp. 16-17

⁷ Singh, B., Chaddha, S. (2018) Globalization and Education. *International Journal of Advanced Educational Research*, 3 (1), p.144.

⁸ Spring, J. (2008) Research on Globalization and Education. *Review of Educational Research*, 78, 2, p. 340.

⁹ Sellar, S., Lingard, B. (2014) The OECD and the expansion of PISA: New Global Modes of Governance in Education. *British Educational Research Journal*, 40, 6, p. 918.

¹⁰ Spring, J. (2014) *Globalization of Education. An Introduction*, 2nd Edition, New York: Routledge, p. 53

¹¹ Kanev, D. (2002) Globalization and Higher Education, *Economic Thought*, 1, pp. 32-33

institutions that form specific practical competencies to develop the potential to facilitate future economic growth. This leads to a convergence of curricula and their adaptation on specific scientific aspects with the potential to influence economic growth. Globalizing sectors of the economy that have a technological or scientific basis requiring specific scientific knowledge and skills include computing and mobile technologies, pharmaceuticals and biotechnology, among others. Countries developing or considering investing in the development of these technologies should be aware of new developments in science and their implications for curricula and programmes as a medium or long-term strategy for successful participation in these sectors.

Another strand of the impact of globalization on HE education relates to the growing role of information and communication technologies (ICTs) and the World Wide Web. The potential impact of this resource on scientific and educational programs is limited to the rapid sharing of scientific information and ideas across a wide range of universities and educational institutions, as well as multinational corporations that provide educational services and curricula and resources to education ministries around the world. ICT helps to increase the quantity and accessibility of learning resources and to implement a differentiated approach to learning tailored to individual needs. They enable rapid information sharing and interaction between learners regardless of their location.

The impact of ICT on the globalization of education is expected to continue to increase as traditional fact-based science curricula are replaced by more flexible curricula focused on the acquisition of specific skills¹². In all spheres of life, and in the field of education, in recent years an important modern trend of development of IT technology related to the mass use of various electronic devices with the help of which communications between people and/or with the external environment can be realized - the "Internet of Things". In education, it can be reduced to the following applied technologies: artificial intelligence systems, virtual classrooms, electronic diaries, cameras for transmitting learning content online, robots¹³, interactive visualization of graphical and other elements through augmented reality, etc.

Globalization is a catalyst for the emergence of new phenomena in university education:

- the emergence of new education service providers in the form of media corporations and multinational companies;
- offering new forms of educational organisation such as distance education;
- taking into account a greater diversification of educational programmes;
- Increase mobility of students, teachers, curricula and educational projects that cross national borders;
- an emphasis on lifelong learning, which in turn leads to increased demand for higher education services;
- increasing private investment in higher education services, etc.

With knowledge transforming into a key driver of economic prosperity and becoming a 'knowledge economy', globalisation is forcing higher education to become a mass necessity. Thus, traditional education systems, from educating a limited number of students, are transformed into systems that encompass and transmit practice-oriented knowledge to ever larger groups of people¹⁴. The response to this by education systems in individual countries has involved the expansion of existing educational institutions and the creation of consortia, affiliates, the introduction of distance and internet learning, and the emergence of new private educational institutions. The impact of the globalization process on higher education can be considered in several aspects: institutional, conceptual, procedural.

¹² Cornali, F., Tirocchi, S. (2012) Globalization, Education, Information and Communication Technologies: What relationships and reciprocal influences? *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 47, p. 2062

¹³ Vitanova, N. (2020) *Aspects of Education 4.0*, Shumen. 93-94.

¹⁴ Fallon, D., M. Ash. (1999) Higher Education in Era of Globalization. *Responses To Globalization in Germany and the United States*, Washington: , American Institute For Contemporary German Studies, pp. 67-78.

The institutional aspect takes into account the influence that global and regional organisations such as UNESCO, the World Bank, the Council of Europe, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, etc. have on higher education systems. They regulate it through the development of international legal instruments and financial instruments, both global and regional. The conceptual aspect is related to the impact of the globalization process on higher education and more precisely on its objectives, principles, methods with a view to forming educational policies for the expansion of intercultural exchange, verification of educational degrees and adaptability to the requirements of practice. The procedural aspect takes into account global educational transformations to develop and implement quality standards for HE education.

As a positive aspect of the globalization impact on the educational processes in the field of higher education can be pointed out the introduction of the system of accumulation and transfer of credits for students, which broadens their horizons and helps them to perceive themselves not only as participants in the learning process, but also as consumers of educational services. The possibility to choose between a large number of courses and educational resources leads to an increase in the flexibility of educational structures and an improvement in the quality of education offered in Bachelor's, Master's and PhD programmes. Contemporary educational trends and learning technologies make the educational process continuous in the form of lifelong learning.

At the same time, many countries are actively implementing such market mechanisms as increased competition between educational institutions as a result of globalisation. This is forcing higher education institutions to emphasize in their educational missions on increasing the advertising activity with the positioning of the results achieved. There is a competition to gain the trust of prospective students, with the help of which higher education institutions can maintain and increase their funding from government subsidy. Globalization as a process also has a negative impact on higher education, which is where we can focus this analysis.

As the education system under the influence of global educational trends is increasingly becoming market-driven, educational institutions are striving to establish new relationships with learners, viewing them as consumers of the educational product produced rather than as participants in the educational process. This distances education from its humanistic essence and from the basic principles of the functioning of the social sphere. The commercial orientation of education in the age of globalization leads to a lowering of fundamental education and ensuring mainly the mastery of educational minimum, as well as paying less and less attention to the existing problems of ethics, social justice, etc.

Another negative relates to providing unequal access to educational resources. Limited access to the World Wide Web in remote regions places financial barriers to those wishing to obtain educational service using modern educational technology. Another negative aspect of quality international education can be pointed out as the financial side, which cannot be secured by socially disadvantaged people, even if student loans are used. As a negative can be pointed out the aspiration to universal unification of educational systems without paying enough attention to the national educational specificity of individual countries, which leads to the destruction of national priorities in their educational systems, which are built on centuries-old cultural and historical traditions. Another negative effect of globalisation on education is the emigration of highly skilled people ("brain drain"), which is becoming the dominant pattern of international migration and a major aspect of globalisation.

According to published data from the Census in the country in 2021, a "brain drain" of more than 2 million people is reported based on the previous census. The same process can be observed in a number of countries in Eastern and Southern Europe, which are having difficulty retaining their young, highly qualified staff. Increased emigration of highly skilled workers and young people can be linked to the Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) and reinforce the drive to migrate to countries with high GCI scores. It is researched by the International Institute for Management Development (IMD), an independent academic institution with Swiss roots and global reach. To calculate the IMD index, countries are analysed and ranked according to their capacity to create and sustain a

competitive environment. Four main factors are considered - economic performance, government effectiveness, business effectiveness and infrastructure. In turn, each of the factors listed is divided into 5 categories that highlight all aspects of the areas analysed. The main pillars of competitiveness emerge as - institutional framework, legislative framework, infrastructure and education.

The economies of 63 countries are analysed for 2022. With the highest competitiveness are the top 5 countries. Bulgaria ranks 53rd with an index of - 51.36¹⁵. In the period 2017-2019, the index for our country ranged from 62.32 to 64.90, after which it dropped sharply and the country retreated from the 48th place.

The reasons are related to the following challenges Bulgaria needs to address:

- Geopolitical turmoil and rising inflation caused by increasing electricity costs;
- Inconsistent policies on energy and climate protection and resources;
- Confrontation between the executive and the judiciary;
- Lack of credible enforcement of anti-corruption measures;
- Limited investment in research, development and innovation¹⁶.

For 2022, three trends emerge that could affect countries' competitiveness in the long term. The first trend is geopolitical issues, which are culminating in renewed armed conflict in Europe and could have global implications for years to come. This could lead to destabilisation of political systems, which in turn are a key element of effective governance.

The second trend concerns existing regional differences in terms of neglecting global risks that could have serious consequences on a global scale. A third trend is seen as the so-called "new globalisation", in which governments need to be more adaptive to changing global conditions and in readiness to meet unexpected threats such as a combination of several crises (health, economic, geopolitical, etc.) operating simultaneously.¹⁷

Within the EU and globally, a workable mechanism is needed to integrate and coordinate policy measures to curb and stop the brain drain. In this respect, work can be done to improve the quality of life in order to attract and retain an educated workforce; to promote policies and instruments for the development of local entrepreneurship, self-employment and alternative business models; and to enhance the role of universities and vocational education, which are linked to the 'knowledge economy'. Today, the contemporary profile of higher education in the context of globalisation is much more dynamic and adaptive as a result of the changes it is experiencing and the need to respond to societal attitudes. It is becoming more systemic, which is caused by the increasing number of challenges it has to solve. The specificity of the time span of its manifestation is peculiar because it necessitates a change in the spiritual values embedded in it and their building on the traditional ones. At the same time, factors related to national traditions and priorities, which influence and should be taken into account, are added to those of a European and global scale. This broadens the 'geography' of possible societal values that should be related to contemporary scientific trends and outlines its recommended frameworks. In addition to developing in a time of transformation of spiritual values, the globalization timeline of higher education requires an adequate response to lay sustainable substantive foundations that will secure its functioning and can be used to build a "new moral landscape" for future generations.

The defining characteristic of contemporary education in the context of globalization can be defined as its mobility. It is typical of modern society and facilitates the elimination of certain borders and the bridging of distances. In the field of higher education, it contributes to the acquisition of experience on the basis of broadening contacts within the scientific community at national and

¹⁵ *Imd world competitiveness booklet* (2022), Lausanne, [tps://imd.cld.bz/IMD-World-Competitiveness-Booklet-2022](https://imd.cld.bz/IMD-World-Competitiveness-Booklet-2022), p. 33

¹⁶ *Ibid*, p. 59

¹⁷ *Ibid*, p. 26

international level. Good shared European and global educational practices enrich the arsenal of didactic competences of university teachers and make them more adaptable and flexible.

An important feature of contemporary education in the context of globalisation is its increased digitisation. The process of increasing digitalization in all spheres of life is completely natural and has its impact on higher education. Its advantages and disadvantages have been confronted by teachers and students in a pandemic environment in the last two years. The problems that have arisen necessitate a search for long-term solutions concerning the need to improve the competencies of university lecturers to work in a digital environment; to increase the quality of digital resources that can be used in the process of distance learning and to provide technical systems and tools for their use; to search for and find mechanisms to obtain adequate feedback from students on the degree of their autonomy in the performance of tasks, etc.

CONCLUSION

The globalization of educational processes leads to a certain unification of education, which is aimed at unification and standardization of educational objectives, of didactic technologies recommended for their use in view of their effectiveness, of national criteria for evaluation. The EU guidelines for educational activities in the European Education Area, etc. serve as a common framework in this respect.

Naturally, unification should not be absolutized, but used creatively to highlight the diversity of educational ideas and their distinctive character in the field of higher education and to link them more closely to business. Educational changes in higher education are taking place at a much greater pace today than they did in the twentieth century. This is caused by the increased dynamics of processes in the modern world and their inevitable impact on education. Relevance as a requirement for the taught educational content causes conditions for rapidly occurring changes also in pedagogical technologies and didactic means. This poses a certain challenge for teachers in higher education institutions to be familiar with and apply current trends in European and world education. In conclusion, it can be pointed out that globalization processes have a complex impact on the characteristics of higher education and lead to its rapid transformation. In this process, a number of challenges are emerging that can be overcome by the efforts of the global academic community with the unifying goal of forming a new public morality.

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